

Electromagnetic stress-energy tensor is a direct consequence of 3- and 6-dimensional left- and right-helical representations of the Lorentz group

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Abstract

We review 3-d reducible representation of the Lorentz group and introduce a 6-d irreducible representation tailored for transforming 6-d electromagnetic vector, and we show that the mixture of the density matrices associated with the left- and right-helical states is equivalent to the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor.

Introduction

There are several ways of transforming the electric and magnetic fields:

1. First transform the 4-vector A^μ

$$A^\mu \rightarrow A'^\mu = \Lambda^\mu{}_\nu A^\nu \quad (1)$$

and then find \vec{E} and \vec{B} from their definitions

$$\vec{E} = -\nabla\phi - \frac{\partial\vec{A}}{\partial t}, \quad \vec{B} = \nabla \times \vec{A} \quad (2)$$

2. Transform the Faraday tensor

$$F^{\mu\nu} \rightarrow F'^{\mu\nu} = \Lambda^\mu{}_\sigma \Lambda^\nu{}_\rho F^{\sigma\rho} \quad (3)$$

where

$$F^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -E_x & -E_y & -E_z \\ E_x & 0 & -B_z & B_y \\ E_y & B_z & 0 & -B_x \\ E_z & -B_y & B_x & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

3. Transform the Riemann-Silberstein vector

$$\xi_L \rightarrow \xi'_L = S_L \xi_L \quad (5)$$

where S_L is an element of the complexified $\text{SO}(3)$ group that corresponds to the left-helicity representation and acts on the Riemann-Silberstein vector ξ_L that represents left-helicity state:

$$\xi_L = \vec{E} - i\vec{B} \quad (6)$$

Similarly, we have right-helicity representation of the complexified $SO(3)$ group S_R that acts on the right-helicity state:

$$\xi_R \rightarrow \xi'_R = S_R \xi_R \quad (7)$$

In a certain representation of basis generators left and right are related with each other by complex conjugation

$$\xi_R = \xi_L^*, \quad S_R = S_L^* \quad (8)$$

It is worth noting that this is a reducible representation that can be expressed as $(1, 0) \oplus (0, 1)$. Full transformation can be written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} S_L & 0 \\ 0 & S_R \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \xi_L \\ \xi_R \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where each block is a 3×3 matrix.

4. Recently we have introduced an irreducible 6-d vector representation of the Lorentz group Λ_6 that can be decomposed into left- and right-helical representations. Λ_6 is especially tailored for transformation of the 6-d real electromagnetic vector \vec{F} :

$$\vec{F} \rightarrow \vec{F}' = \Lambda_6 \vec{F}, \quad \text{where} \quad \vec{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{E} \\ \vec{B} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

It can be shown that Λ_6 can be written as a matrix product of 6-d left- and right-representations: $\Lambda_6 = \mathcal{H}_L \mathcal{H}_R$. In the chosen basis $\mathcal{H}_R = \mathcal{H}_L^*$.

Left-helical representation \mathcal{H}_L acts on the 6-component left-helical state \mathcal{F}_L :

$$\mathcal{F}_L \rightarrow \mathcal{F}'_L = \mathcal{H}_L \mathcal{F}_L \quad \text{where} \quad \mathcal{F}_L = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_L \\ i\xi_L \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Similarly, right-helical representation \mathcal{H}_R acts on the 6-component right-helical state \mathcal{F}_R :

$$\mathcal{F}_R \rightarrow \mathcal{F}'_R = \mathcal{H}_R \mathcal{F}_R \quad \text{where} \quad \mathcal{F}_R = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_R \\ -i\xi_R \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

1.

Lie algebras of the representations mentioned in cases 1-4 are all the same, namely the Lorentz algebra. In order to be self contained detailed information is given in the Appendix.

In this note we will show that the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor is a direct consequence of the 3- and 6-dimensional representations.

Electromagnetic stress-energy tensor

Electromagnetic stress-energy tensor is a traceless symmetric tensor and it is given by

$$T^{00} = \frac{1}{2}(E^2 + B^2), \quad T^{0i} = (\vec{E} \otimes \vec{B})_i, \quad T^{ij} = -(E_i E_j + B_i B_j) + \frac{1}{2}(E^2 + B^2)\delta^{ij} \quad (13)$$

¹We have $\mathcal{F}_L^\dagger \mathcal{F}_R = 0$, but $\xi_L^\dagger \xi_R \neq 0$

It is straightforward to show that elements of this stress-energy tensor directly emerge from the tensor product of the helical states:

$$\mathcal{T} = \mathcal{F}_L \mathcal{F}_L^\dagger + \mathcal{F}_R \mathcal{F}_R^\dagger \quad (14)$$

which transforms as

$$\mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathcal{T}' = \mathcal{H}_L(\mathcal{F}_L \mathcal{F}_L^\dagger) \mathcal{H}_L^\dagger + \mathcal{H}_R(\mathcal{F}_R \mathcal{F}_R^\dagger) \mathcal{H}_R^\dagger \quad (15)$$

² Explicit form of \mathcal{T} is given by

$$\mathcal{T} = \begin{pmatrix} E_1^2 + B_1^2 & E_1 E_2 + B_1 B_2 & E_1 E_3 + B_1 B_3 & 0 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 & -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 \\ E_2 E_1 + B_2 B_1 & E_2^2 + B_2^2 & E_2 E_3 + B_2 B_3 & -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 & 0 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 \\ E_3 E_1 + B_3 B_1 & E_3 E_2 + B_3 B_2 & E_3^2 + B_3^2 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 & -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 & E_1^2 + B_1^2 & E_1 E_2 + B_1 B_2 & E_1 E_3 + B_1 B_3 \\ (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 & 0 & -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 & E_2 E_1 + B_2 B_1 & E_2^2 + B_2^2 & E_2 E_3 + B_2 B_3 \\ -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 & 0 & E_3 E_1 + B_3 B_1 & E_3 E_2 + B_3 B_2 & E_3^2 + B_3^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

\mathcal{T} is neither symmetric nor traceless, but it is equivalent to $T^{\mu\nu}$. All elements of $T^{\mu\nu}$ can be directly read off from the elements of \mathcal{T} . For example, $\text{tr} \mathcal{T}$ gives T^{00} , etc. Here we write $T^{\mu\nu}$ in matrix form for reference:

$$T^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}(E^2 + B^2) & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 \\ (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 & \frac{1}{2}(E^2 + B^2) - (E_1^2 + B_1^2) & -(E_1 E_2 + B_1 B_2) & -(E_1 E_3 + B_1 B_3) \\ (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 & -(E_2 E_1 + B_2 B_1) & \frac{1}{2}(E^2 + B^2) - (E_2^2 + B_2^2) & -(E_2 E_3 + B_2 B_3) \\ (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 & -(E_3 E_1 + B_3 B_1) & -(E_3 E_2 + B_3 B_2) & \frac{1}{2}(E^2 + B^2) - (E_3^2 + B_3^2) \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Equivalently, It is also possible to obtain the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor directly from the Riemann-Silbestein vectors:

$$\xi_L \xi_L^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} E_1^2 + B_1^2 & E_1 E_2 + B_1 B_2 & E_1 E_3 + B_1 B_3 \\ E_2 E_1 + B_2 B_1 & E_2^2 + B_2^2 & E_2 E_3 + B_2 B_3 \\ E_3 E_1 + B_3 B_1 & E_3 E_2 + B_3 B_2 & E_3^2 + B_3^2 \end{pmatrix} + i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 & -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 \\ -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 & 0 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 \\ (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 & -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$\xi_L \xi_L^\dagger$ represents a pure state. Imaginary part gives the Poynting vector. All elements of the stress-energy tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ can be read from $\xi_L \xi_L^\dagger$. Similarly we write the density matrix corresponding to the pure state $\xi_R \xi_R^\dagger$:

$$\xi_R \xi_R^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} E_1^2 + B_1^2 & E_1 E_2 + B_1 B_2 & E_1 E_3 + B_1 B_3 \\ E_2 E_1 + B_2 B_1 & E_2^2 + B_2^2 & E_2 E_3 + B_2 B_3 \\ E_3 E_1 + B_3 B_1 & E_3 E_2 + B_3 B_2 & E_3^2 + B_3^2 \end{pmatrix} - i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 & -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 \\ -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_3 & 0 & (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 \\ (\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_2 & -(\vec{E} \times \vec{B})_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Now write the mixture of states $\xi_L \xi_L^\dagger$ and $\xi_R \xi_R^\dagger$:

$$\xi_L \xi_L^\dagger + \xi_R \xi_R^\dagger = 2 \begin{pmatrix} E_1^2 + B_1^2 & E_1 E_2 + B_1 B_2 & E_1 E_3 + B_1 B_3 \\ E_2 E_1 + B_2 B_1 & E_2^2 + B_2^2 & E_2 E_3 + B_2 B_3 \\ E_3 E_1 + B_3 B_1 & E_3 E_2 + B_3 B_2 & E_3^2 + B_3^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

We get a density matrix of a mixture with no Poynting vector.

²Since $\mathcal{F}_R = \mathcal{F}_L^*$, $\mathcal{T} = 2\text{Re}(\mathcal{F}_L \mathcal{F}_L^\dagger)$

Appendix

1. $(1, 0) \oplus (0, 1)$ reducible representation of the Lorentz group

Generators of the complexified $\text{SO}(3)$ group:

$$J_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad J_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad J_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (21)$$

$$K_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad K_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad K_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (22)$$

We have the following commutation relations:

$$[J_i, J_j] = \epsilon_{ijk} J_k, \quad [K_i, K_j] = -\epsilon_{ijk} J_k, \quad [J_i, K_j] = \epsilon_{ijk} K_k \quad (23)$$

This is the algebra of the Lorentz group. In terms of these generators we can write S_L and S_R as follows:

$$S_L = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)J_i}, \quad S_R = e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)J_i} \quad (24)$$

where θ_i and ϕ_i are the rotation and boost parameters respectively.

It is worth noting that this is a reducible representation that can be expressed as $(1, 0) \oplus (0, 1)$. Full transformation can be written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} S_L & 0 \\ 0 & S_R \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \xi_L \\ \xi_R \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

each block is a 3×3 matrix.

2. Six-dimensional irreducible representations of the Lorentz group

2.1. Extension and complexification of the group $\text{SO}(3)$

Let \vec{F} be the 6-component electromagnetic vector:

$$\vec{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{E} \\ \vec{B} \end{pmatrix} \quad (26)$$

And let Λ_6 be a 6×6 Lorentz transformation matrix acting on \vec{F} that can be written in terms of parameters θ_i and ϕ_i and rotation and boost generators J_i and K_i :

$$\Lambda_6 = e^{(\theta_i J_i + \phi_i K_i)} \quad (27)$$

where

$$J_1 = e \otimes S_1, \quad J_2 = e \otimes S_2, \quad J_3 = e \otimes S_3 \quad (28)$$

$$K_1 = \epsilon \otimes S_1, \quad K_2 = \epsilon \otimes S_2, \quad K_3 = \epsilon \otimes S_3 \quad (29)$$

S_1, S_2, S_3 are the generators of the SO(3) group and e and ϵ are the extension units with the properties, $e^2 = \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2}$, $\epsilon^2 = -\mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2}$:

$$e = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (30)$$

In this irreducible representation ϵ plays the role of the imaginary unit and serves for the complexification of the algebra.

We have the following commutation relations:

$$[J_i, J_j] = \epsilon_{ijk} J_k, \quad [K_i, K_j] = -\epsilon_{ijk} J_k, \quad [J_i, K_j] = \epsilon_{ijk} K_k \quad (31)$$

This is the algebra of SO(1,3).

Under the rotations electric and magnetic field vectors rotate independently. Boosts are more interesting. Explicit form of a boost in an arbitrary direction and its action on \vec{F} reads

$$\begin{pmatrix} E'_x \\ E'_y \\ E'_z \\ B'_x \\ B'_y \\ B'_z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma + \frac{\beta_x^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_x\beta_y(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_x\beta_z(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & 0 & -\beta_z\gamma & \beta_y\gamma \\ \frac{\beta_y\beta_x(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \gamma + \frac{\beta_y^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_y\beta_z(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \beta_z\gamma & 0 & -\beta_x\gamma \\ \frac{\beta_z\beta_x(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_z\beta_y(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \gamma + \frac{\beta_z^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & -\beta_y\gamma & \beta_x\gamma & 0 \\ 0 & \beta_z\gamma & -\beta_y\gamma & \gamma + \frac{\beta_x^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_x\beta_y(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_x\beta_z(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} \\ -\beta_z\gamma & 0 & \beta_x\gamma & \frac{\beta_y\beta_x(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \gamma + \frac{\beta_y^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_y\beta_z(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} \\ \beta_y\gamma & -\beta_x\gamma & 0 & \frac{\beta_z\beta_x(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_z\beta_y(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \gamma + \frac{\beta_z^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E_x \\ E_y \\ E_z \\ B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (32)$$

The irreducible representation Λ_6 preserves a metric g which plays the role of the Minkowski metric:

$$\Lambda_6^T g \Lambda_6 = g, \quad \text{where,} \quad g = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (33)$$

With this metric we can define the scalar product and obtain one of the Lorentz invariants of the electromagnetic field:

$$\vec{F} \cdot \vec{F} = \vec{F}^T g \vec{F} = |\vec{E}|^2 - |\vec{B}|^2 \quad (34)$$

3.2. Left- and right-helical representations

Let us define new generators:

$$M_i = \frac{1}{2}(J_i - iK_i) = \frac{1}{2}(e \otimes S_i - i\epsilon \otimes S_i) = h \otimes S_i, \quad N_i = \frac{1}{2}(J_i + iK_i) = \frac{1}{2}(e \otimes S_i + i\epsilon \otimes S_i) = h^* \otimes S_i \quad (35)$$

where

$$h = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -i \\ i & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad h^n = h, \quad hh^* = 0 \quad (36)$$

M_i and N_i obey the SU(2) algebra and commute with each other. We rewrite Λ_6 in terms of M_i and N_i or equivalently in terms of $h \otimes S_i$ and $h^* \otimes S_i$:

$$\Lambda_6 = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)h \otimes S_i + (\theta_i - i\phi_i)h^* \otimes S_i} \quad (37)$$

Let us denote $\mathcal{H}_L = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)h \otimes S_i}$ and $\mathcal{H}_R = e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)h^* \otimes S_i}$. Since $[M_i, N_j] = 0$, Λ_6 can be written as matrix product, $\Lambda_6 = \mathcal{H}_L \mathcal{H}_R$, where \mathcal{H}_L and \mathcal{H}_R can be regarded as 6-dimensional left- and right-helical irreducible representations. \mathcal{H}_L acts on the left-helical state \mathcal{F}_L ³:

$$\mathcal{F}_L = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{E} \\ i\mathcal{E} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \text{where} \quad \mathcal{E} = \vec{E} - i\vec{B} \quad (38)$$

As an example let us write the boost matrix in the x -direction for \mathcal{H}_L

$$\mathcal{H}_L = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cosh \phi) & -\frac{i}{2} \sinh \phi & 0 & \frac{i}{2}(1 - \cosh \phi) & -\frac{1}{2} \sinh \phi \\ 0 & \frac{i}{2} \sinh \phi & \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cosh \phi) & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \sinh \phi & \frac{i}{2}(1 - \cosh \phi) \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{i}{2}(1 - \cosh \phi) & \frac{1}{2} \sinh \phi & 0 & \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cosh \phi) & -\frac{i}{2} \sinh \phi \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} \sinh \phi & -\frac{i}{2}(1 - \cosh \phi) & 0 & \frac{i}{2} \sinh \phi & \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cosh \phi) \end{pmatrix} \quad (39)$$

Similar expressions can be written for the right-helical representation.

The metric g that given in Eq.(33) is also preserved by \mathcal{H}_L and \mathcal{H}_R :

$$\mathcal{H}_L^T g \mathcal{H}_L = g, \quad \mathcal{H}_R^T g \mathcal{H}_R = g \quad (40)$$

Hence we can define the scalar product of helical states and find the associated Lorentz invariants:

$$\mathcal{F}_L \cdot \mathcal{F}_L = \mathcal{F}_L^T g \mathcal{F}_L = |\vec{E}|^2 - |\vec{B}|^2 - 2i\vec{E} \cdot \vec{B} \quad (41)$$

3.2 Weyl-like equations for left- and right-helical states

Let $\Sigma = i(S_x, S_y, S_z)$, where S_i is given in Eq.(30), and let us define the operator $\Sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}$:

$$\Sigma \cdot \mathbf{n} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -ic & is\phi \\ ic & 0 & -is\phi \\ -is\phi & is\phi & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (42)$$

where $\mathbf{n} = (\sin \theta \cos \phi, \sin \theta \sin \phi, \cos \theta)$ and $c = \cos \theta$, $s = \sin \theta$, $\phi = \cos \phi$, $\phi = \sin \phi$. $\Sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}$ is a traceless Hermitian matrix and it has 3 orthogonal eigenvectors corresponding to the eigenvalues ± 1 and 0.

$$\varphi_+ = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -c\phi + i\phi \\ -c\phi - i\phi \\ s \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_- = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -c\phi - i\phi \\ -c\phi + i\phi \\ s \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_0 = \begin{pmatrix} s\phi \\ s\phi \\ c \end{pmatrix} \quad (43)$$

³In this representation $\mathcal{H}_R = \mathcal{H}_L^*$, but this is not true in general.

Actually, these are 3-component objects similar to the Weyl spinors, and they are the solutions to the following version of the Weyl equations:

$$(i\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p})\psi = 0 \quad (44)$$

$$(i\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p})\chi = 0 \quad (45)$$

where $\mathbf{p} = |\mathbf{p}|\mathbf{n}$. Plane wave ansatz suggest that φ_+ and φ_- are the solutions that can be associated with right- and left-helicity states.

We can also make the connection between φ_{\pm} and $\xi_{R,L}$. Let us start with Eq.(44) and suppose that $E=|\mathbf{p}| > 0$ and assume that ξ_L satisfies the equation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & -ic & is\cancel{\phi} \\ ic & -1 & -is\cancel{\phi} \\ -is\cancel{\phi} & is\cancel{\phi} & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E_x - iB_x \\ E_y - iB_y \\ E_z - iB_z \end{pmatrix} = 0 \quad (46)$$

This matrix equation gives 4 linearly independent equations to be solved for E_i and B_i . Taking E_3 and B_3 as free variables we get the following expressions:

$$E_1 = (-c\cancel{\phi}E_3 - \cancel{\phi}B_3)/s, \quad E_2 = (-c\cancel{\phi}E_3 + \cancel{\phi}B_3)/s, \quad B_1 = (-c\cancel{\phi}B_3 + \cancel{\phi}E_3)/s, \quad B_2 = (-c\cancel{\phi}B_3 - \cancel{\phi}E_3)/s \quad (47)$$

Hence, ξ_L can be written as

$$\xi_L = \begin{pmatrix} E_x - iB_x \\ E_y - iB_y \\ E_z - iB_z \end{pmatrix} = \frac{E_3 - iB_3}{s} \begin{pmatrix} -c\cancel{\phi} - i\cancel{\phi} \\ -c\cancel{\phi} + i\cancel{\phi} \\ s \end{pmatrix} = \frac{E_3 - iB_3}{s} \varphi_L \quad (48)$$

Similar expression can be written for ξ_R by simply taking the complex conjugate of ξ_L .

$$\xi_R = \begin{pmatrix} E_x + iB_x \\ E_y + iB_y \\ E_z + iB_z \end{pmatrix} = \frac{E_3 + iB_3}{s} \begin{pmatrix} -c\cancel{\phi} + i\cancel{\phi} \\ -c\cancel{\phi} - i\cancel{\phi} \\ s \end{pmatrix} = \frac{E_3 + iB_3}{s} \varphi_R \quad (49)$$

3.3 Duals and their transformations

Let $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_L$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R$ be the duals of \mathcal{F}_L and \mathcal{F}_R :

$$\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_L = g\mathcal{F}_L = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{E}_L \\ -i\mathcal{E}_L \end{pmatrix}, \quad \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R = g\mathcal{F}_R = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{E}_R \\ i\mathcal{E}_R \end{pmatrix}, \quad \text{where } \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R = \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_L^* \quad (50)$$

It can be shown that $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R$ transforms as follows:

$$\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{F}}'_R = (\mathcal{H}_L^{-1})^\dagger \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R \quad (51)$$

Here we have the property:

$$(\mathcal{H}_L^{-1})^\dagger = g\mathcal{H}_L^*g^{-1} \quad (52)$$

Similarity to the Weyl spinors and their transformation properties can be made more clear by using the Infeld-Van der Weerden notation:

$$\mathcal{F}_L = \mathcal{F}_R^* = \mathcal{F}_a, \quad \mathcal{F}_L^* = \mathcal{F}_R = \mathcal{F}_{\dot{a}}, \quad \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_L = \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R^* = \mathcal{F}^a, \quad \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_L^* = \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R = \mathcal{F}^{\dot{a}} \quad (53)$$

3.4 Parity transformation

Under the parity \vec{E} transforms as a vector and \vec{B} transforms as an axial vector:

$$\vec{E} \xrightarrow{P} -\vec{E}, \quad \vec{B} \xrightarrow{P} \vec{B} \quad (54)$$

Accordingly, under the parity inversion the Riemann-Silberstein vector transforms as

$$\xi_L = \vec{E} - i\vec{B} \xrightarrow{P} -\vec{E} - i\vec{B} = -\xi_L^* = -\xi_R, \quad (55)$$

$$\xi_R = \vec{E} + i\vec{B} \xrightarrow{P} -\vec{E} + i\vec{B} = -\xi_R^* = -\xi_L, \quad (56)$$

On the other hand, under the parity inversion left- and right-helical states behave in a different way:

$$\mathcal{F}_L = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_L \\ i\xi_L \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{P} \begin{pmatrix} -\xi_L^* \\ -i\xi_L^* \end{pmatrix} = -\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R, \quad \text{similarly} \quad \mathcal{F}_R \xrightarrow{P} -\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_L \quad (57)$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_L = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_L \\ -i\xi_L \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{P} \begin{pmatrix} -\xi_L^* \\ i\xi_L^* \end{pmatrix} = -\mathcal{F}_R \quad \text{similarly} \quad \tilde{\mathcal{F}}_R \xrightarrow{P} -\mathcal{F}_L \quad (58)$$

It may be easier to see these transformation properties of the helical states in the Infeld-Van der Weerden notation

$$\mathcal{F}_a \xrightarrow{P} -\mathcal{F}^{\dot{a}}, \quad \mathcal{F}_{\dot{a}} \xrightarrow{P} -\mathcal{F}^a, \quad \mathcal{F}^a \xrightarrow{P} -\mathcal{F}_{\dot{a}}, \quad \mathcal{F}^{\dot{a}} \xrightarrow{P} -\mathcal{F}_a \quad (59)$$

Minus signs in these relations have no significance. We can get rid of them by simply redefining g as $-g$.

References

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